

STYLISTIC FEATURES OF ORATORICAL STYLE

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Annotation: The article deals with the stylistic features of the oratorical style which is the oral subdivision of the publicistic style. Different opinions of scientists on are problem are considered. Bright examples of speeches of well known persons are analyzed from stylistic point of view.

Изох: Maqolada publitsistik uslubning og'zaki bo'limi bo'lgan notqlik uslubining stilistik xususiyatlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Muammo bo'yicha olimlarning turli fikrlari urganilgan. Taniqli shaxslar nutqining yorqin namunalari stilistik nuqtai nazardan tahlil qilingan.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются стилистические особенности ораторского стиля, который является устным подразделением публицистического стиля. Рассмотрены различные мнения ученых по данной проблеме. Со стилистической точки зрения анализируются яркие примеры выступлений известных личностей.

In ancient Greece, the ability to speak eloquently was considered an art. However, the classification was mainly carried out only between crookedness, poetry and actor's creativity. Rhetoric was primarily interpreted as the science of word and poetry, prose and eloquence. The speaker is both a poet and a master of the word.

In antiquity, rhetoric was taught. Speakers are most resorted to exceptionally poetic techniques, with a view to strengthening the expressiveness of his speech. Today the speech genre define the depending on the communication sphere, corresponding to its own function: communication, communication and impact Russian judicial speaker Konni A.F. wrote about the skill of public appearances as a true creativity, including artistry and elements of poetry expressed in verbal form. A speaker is a person who must necessarily have a creative imagination. According to Konni, the difference between a poet and an orator is that they come to the same reality, starting from different points of view [1].

In the article we'll try to analyze some stylistic features of oratorical style.

The oratorical style is the oral subdivision of the publicistic style. The most obvious purpose of oratory is persuasion, and it requires eloquence [2]. This style is evident in speeches on political and social problems of the day, in orations and addresses on solemn occasions as public weddings, funerals and jubilees, in sermons and debates and also in the speeches of counsel and judges in courts of law.

The sphere of application of oratory is confined to appeal to an audience and therefore crucial issues in such spheres as science, art, or business relations are not touched upon.

Direct contact with the listeners permits the combination of the syntactical, lexical and phonetic peculiarities of both the written and spoken varieties of language. In its leading feature, however, the oratorical style belongs to the written variety of language, though it is modified by the oral form of the utterance and the use of gestures.

Like the colloquial style, oratory is usually characterized by emotional colouring and connotations, but there is a difference. The emotional colouring of the publicist style is lofty – it may be solemn, or ironic, but it cannot have the “lowered” connotations (jocular, rude, vulgar, or slangy) found in colloquial speech [3]. The vocabulary of speeches is usually elaborately chosen and remains mainly in the sphere of high-flown style. We’ ll try to analyze next examples of speeches:

Four score and seven years ago our fathers brought forth on this continent, a new nation, conceived and so dedicated in Liberty, and dedicated to the proposition that all men are created equal. Now we are engaged in a great civil war, testing whether that nation, or any nation so conceived, can long endure. We are met on a great battle-field of that war. We have come to dedicate a portion of that field, as a final resting place for those who here gave their lives that that nation might live. It is altogether fitting and proper that we should do this (A. Lincoln, The Gettysburg Address).

The stylistic devices employed in the oratorical style are determined by the conditions of communication. If the desire of the speaker is to rouse the audience and to keep it in suspense, he will use various traditional stylistic devices. Stylistic devices are closely interwoven and mutually complementary thus building up an intricate pattern. For example, an antithesis is framed by parallel constructions, which, in their turn, are accompanied by repetition, while a climax can be formed by repetitions of different kinds.

But, in a larger sense, **we cannot dedicate – we cannot consecrate – we cannot hallow** this ground. The brave men, living and dead, who struggled here, have consecrated it, far above our poor power to add or detract. The world will little note, nor long remember what we say here, but it can never forget what they did here. **It is for us the living, rather, to be dedicated** here to the unfinished work which they who fought here have thus far so nobly advanced. **It is rather for us to be dedicated** to the great task remaining before us – that from these honoured dead we take increased devotion to that cause for which they gave the last full measure of devotion – that we here highly resolve that these dead **shall not have died in vain** – that this nation, under God, **shall have a new birth of freedom** – and that the government of

the people, by the people, for the people, **shall not perish** from the earth [A. Lincoln].

As the audience rely only on memory, the speaker often resorts to repetition to enable his listeners to follow him and retain the main points of the speech. Repetition is also resorted to in order to persuade the audience, to add weight to the speaker’s opinion. The following extract from the speech of the American Confederate general, A.P. Hill, on the ending of the Civil War in the U.S.A. is an example of anaphoric repetition:

It is high time this people had recovered from the passions of war. **It is high time** that counsel were taken from statesmen, not demagogues... **It is high time** the people of the North and South understood each other and adopted means to inspire confidence in each other.

A mere repetition of the same idea and in the same linguistic form may bore the audience and destroy the speaker-audience contact, therefore synonymous phrase repetition is used instead, thus filling up the speech with details and embellishing it, as in this excerpt from a speech on Robert Burns:

For Burns exalted our race, he hallowed Scotland and the Scottish tongue. Before his time we had for a long period been scarcely recognized; we had been falling out of recollection of the world. From the time of the Union of the Crowns, and still more from the legislative union, Scotland had lapsed into obscurity. Except for an occasional riot, or a Jacobite rising, her existence was almost forgotten. (All those different phrases simply repeat the idea “ nobody knew us, Scots, before”).

Repetition can be regarded as the most typical stylistic device of the English oratorical style.

In conclusion we may underline the fact that almost any piece of oratory will have parallel constructions, antithesis, climax, rhetorical questions and questions-in-the-narrative. It will be no exaggeration to say that almost all typical syntactical devices can be found in English oratory.

References:

1. I. V. Arnold. Stylistics. Modern English. - Moscow, 2002.
2. Yu. M. Skrebnev. Fundamentals of stylistics. - Moscow, 2002.
3. I. R. Galperin. Stylistics. - Moscow, 1977.

